

**MODERN RECEPTIONS OF «GREEN» STANDARD
FOR FITNESS CENTERS**

Savchenko Natasha

student

Oliinyk Tatiana

Semenova Svetlana

PhD in Technical Sciences

Odessa State Academy of Civil Engineering and of Architecture (Ukraine)

***Abstract.** The sports industry is gaining more and more importance in the life of modern society and of every person in particular. As a result of the study of the prevalence of sports facilities in Ukraine, it was found that fitness clubs have the largest share of the market in cities. This is due to popularization of fitness at the highest level and stimulation of Ukrainians to a healthy lifestyle.*

Modern fitness in Ukraine has developed over the past 10-15 years. People began to think about the importance of training for human health, about the benefits of a healthy lifestyle and the consequences of lack of physical exercise. Today, all the cities of our country have a variety of specialized fitness centers and clubs which provide various complexes of fitness programs.

The design of fitness centers requires certain requirements. Today, there is no document that fully meets the modern requirements for designing a fitness facility. In the current DBN V.2.2-13-2003 "Sports and physical culture and health facilities" determine only the issue of the location of sports facilities, the distribution of functional zones and technical support. It is impossible to design clubs according to one pattern. Thoughtful and professionally implemented interior of the club - ensures its success, gives uniqueness and makes it competitive.

The topic of introducing modern eco-design methods in the interiors of fitness clubs is relevant. The problem is that the use of living plants in the interior design of sports facilities is quite limited in Ukraine. The implementation of greening in the practice of designing and building fitness centers will improve the environmental friendliness of buildings, the level of comfort of stay, and improve the architecture of buildings. Phytodesign is becoming a modern and popular method of interior landscaping - the introduction of plants into interior design, taking into account their biological, ecological and aesthetic features. Phytocompositions are used for decorating and visual zoning of spaces, creating an aesthetically attractive atmosphere.

Keywords: *fitness center, landscaping, microclimate, green architecture, design.*

Relevance of research. The topic of introducing modern eco-design methods in the interiors of fitness clubs is relevant. The problem is that the use of living plants in the interior design of sports facilities is limited in Ukraine. The implementation of landscaping in the practice of designing and building fitness centers will improve the environmental friendliness of buildings, the level of comfort, and improve the architecture of buildings.

Today, meeting the requirements of "green" standards is a priority direction in the development of the typology of fitness centers with a developed functional composition and planning organization. The principles of "green" construction or eco-architecture will contribute to the energy-efficient use of resources, the satisfaction of the principles of sustainable development, the modern development of the city's architecture, and will also involve cultural ways of spending leisure time and improving the health of the nation.

Scientific novelty. Using the example of a fitness center project in Odesa (Ukraine), the use of plants for greening sports facilities was analyzed; determining

the optimal architectural and planning and compositional methods of phytodesign of the interior of the premises.

The task of high-quality design of fitness centers requires studying the centuries-old theoretical and practical history of the construction of sports facilities [1].

Analysis of design experience and prerequisites for the formation of sports complexes

For the competent design of sports buildings and complexes, a comprehensive analysis of the history of the formation and development of sports facilities and an assessment of their role in the social life of mankind is necessary. The study of the main trends of international sports architecture at various stages of its formation is an important requirement when designing modern sports facilities [1].

Sports have accompanied the life of human society since ancient times. Physical culture and sport have their historical roots dating back to ancient times. The history of sports facilities consists of the following periods: *primitive-communal, slave-owning, the Middle Ages, and modern times*. Archaeological excavations provide information about primitive structures for physical exercises that date back to the Stone Age. The petroglyphs testify that already the cave people organized competitions in the open air to pass tests [2].

Sports buildings in Ancient Greece and Rome. In ancient times, physical exercises had a cult character and were associated with hygiene, military training, games, and entertainment. The development of physical education necessitated the construction of special facilities. The spirit of good neighborliness and peaceful competition is reflected in the architectural design of stadiums in Ancient Greece. Greek stadiums differed in perfect architectural forms, grand scale and harmoniously fit into the surrounding landscape (Fig. 1). There were several types of buildings: gymnasium - a rectangular building with a special playground for walks and exercises; the stadium - a rectangular building was located between the hills; hippodrome - had the shape of a horseshoe with tracks covered with sand.

The buildings of Ancient Rome were designed for gladiatorial combat and were multi-storied, circular structures with a fighting arena in the center, such as the Colosseum. The stadiums of this period become architecturally finished objects. Their form had a significant impact on the construction of modern sports arenas.

Fig. 1. Sports facilities of Ancient Greece and Ancient Rome

The Middle Ages. The early Middle Ages is characterized by a complete decline of physical culture. Sports facilities were not built because the church was opposed to physical exercises (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Sports games in the Middle Ages

Only feudal lords participated in knightly tournaments. In the 16th and 17th centuries, in many cities, special areas were set aside for public ball games and target shooting. The Middle Ages became famous for sports games. The period of the late

Middle Ages - the birth of bourgeois physical culture gradually saw the revival of the role of sports facilities .

From modern times to the present day. Starting from the 19th century, the role of sports facilities began to gradually revive. Fans of German, French, and Swedish gymnastics began to build small sports grounds (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Sports grounds of the New Age

The era of modern sports began with the protection of human health from the impact of industrialization: swimming pools (Germany, 1828; Holland, 1830); football pitches (1855). In the 20th century under the influence of technical progress and socio-political reforms, all types of sports began to develop intensively. This required the construction of special sports facilities of various types and designs. The appearance of new materials in construction led to changes in the architecture of sports facilities. In terms of functionality, modern sports facilities have mostly preserved common features with ancient buildings (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Modern stadium architecture

Features of the organization of fitness centers

In recent decades, the attitude of citizens towards sports and a healthy lifestyle has been changing in a positive direction. The number of people engaged in fitness has increased significantly.

The requirements for the design and construction of sports facilities are changing. More attention is paid to the application of ecological and innovative solutions and meeting the requirements of the modern consumer. The analysis of advanced international experience in the design of fitness objects showed that there are the following features of their organization: a developed composition of functional zones; additional accompanying service; use of the adjacent territory; compliance with "green" standards. In the architectural and planning decisions of fitness facilities, the following are distinguished: main functional areas; additional multifunctional zones; auxiliary, public, commercial and service. The main architectural and planning principles of the organization of fitness centers: *the principle of accessibility, the principle of social targeting; principle of functionality; the principle of transformation; principle of ergonomics; the principle of natural integration; principle of manufacturability; the principle of environmental safety* [3].

One of the main requirements for the design of modern fitness centers is the principle of environmental safety, which takes into account microclimatic and sanitary and hygienic requirements for the parameters of the premises. A fitness club is a space for physical activity. He should be charged with energy and cheerfulness. Therefore, the quality of the air in the halls of the fitness center is of particular importance. During training, people's oxygen consumption increases, a person begins to breathe through the mouth, bypassing the body's natural filter - the nose, which reduces immunity and increases the risk of infection. In the process of training, a person's heartbeat accelerates, which leads to increased breathing. Accelerated breathing helps to increase the content of carbon dioxide in the air, and accordingly, the amount of oxygen during inhalation decreases. This causes a feeling of suffocation, rapid fatigue and reduces the effectiveness of training. Numerous

scientific studies have shown that high levels of dust, carbon dioxide, formaldehyde and other volatile organic compounds are established in sports halls. Concentrations of these substances mostly exceed indoor air quality standards (Fig. 5) [4].

Fig. 5. Premises of fitness centers

Another problem of the environment of sports facilities is mold and fungus, which is formed due to high humidity. They destroy sports equipment and have a serious detrimental effect on human health. Developing in the pool, showers and changing rooms, fungal colonies harm the reputation of the institution, but most importantly harm human health. Closed windows, stagnant air, accumulation of carbon dioxide exhaled by a person, dust on interior surfaces and walls all lead to deterioration of air quality. Air in a closed space can be several times more toxic and dangerous than outside.

Sanitary and hygienic requirements for sports halls

Sports facilities must meet certain hygienic requirements that provide optimal conditions for people engaged in physical culture and sports. These requirements are regulated by relevant building and sanitary norms and rules, industry regulatory and methodical documents. Particularly high hygienic requirements are applied to sports facilities, since the health-improving effect of physical exercises and sports depends on their sanitary condition [5].

The air-heat regime of sports facilities is subject to hygienic regulation, as it significantly affects the heat exchange of people. Optimal humidity - 30-50%, air

movement - 0.06-0.25 m/s, temperature 15-17 °C. A special sanitary and hygienic regime is established for artificial indoor swimming pools: air temperature + 24 ° - + 27 ° C, water temperature - from + 26 ° to + 29 ° C. Water quality must meet the requirements for drinking water.

To ensure the necessary air exchange, it is planned to install central supply and exhaust ventilation. A properly designed gym ventilation system is crucial, as ventilation ensures the correct balance of gases and ensures that the air you breathe does not contain too much carbon dioxide. The ventilation of the fitness center should be sufficient. Each of the visitors must receive the necessary amount of oxygen. From a medical point of view, the influx of fresh air is necessary for "feeding" muscle tissue and facilitating their work, as well as for sufficient blood supply to the parts of the body that are being trained.

Properly designed pool ventilation normalizes the level of moisture content in the air, ensures the absence of condensation and excess moisture, reduces the likelihood of mold and fungus in the room to almost zero.

The role of ecodesign in forming the microclimate of fitness clubs

Modern architects use phytodesign to create a favorable, comfortable and safe environment in the premises of fitness clubs. Plants are an important addition to the air conditioning system. Plants and green areas are an additional source of fresh air. Their use in the premises allows to increase the quality and cleanliness of the air; will provide an optimal combination of gases in the air environment; will make the air safer to breathe.

Plants in the halls remove odors and pollution from the environment, provide humidity control; contribute to the improvement of the microclimate and sanitary and hygienic conditions of the environment. Plants reduce stress and have a positive psycho-emotional effect. Green color has a calming effect, reduces irritability, improves mood. Plants reduce the negative impact of electromagnetic waves, leveling the internal background [6].

The use of green plants for sports centers is focused not only on the aesthetic appeal of the project being created, but also on its practical validity (Fig. 6). The practical goals of filling indoor spaces with greenery include a number of advantages: reducing the need for air conditioning and saving electricity; air humidification; green leaves produce oxygen [7].

Fig. 6. Properties of plants

The use of green plants and the basic techniques of phytodesign in the formation of the interior space of sports centers solves a number of tasks: aesthetic - the mental effect of plants on a person with the help of the beauty of form and color; improvement of the air environment (tonic, soothing smells); disinfection and improvement of the environment due to volatile phytoncides; air purification from gases, dust, smoke; noise reduction by plants; bioindication, i.e. the use of plants as living indicators of air, soil and water pollution; study of the condition of the plants

themselves in the interiors in order to select the most effective and well-growing species [8].

There are certain landscaping methods for the premises of fitness centers. The analysis of the best international experience in the design of fitness facilities showed that a great deal of attention is paid in the projects to the application of ecological and innovative solutions that meet the requirements of green construction. Phytodesign of the interior and greening of fitness centers is a very relevant trend in world eco-architecture (Fig. 7).

Fig.7. Foreign experience in phytodesign of gym interiors

However, many popular fitness centers in Ukraine do not take this into account (Fig. 8). A review of fitness centers in Ukraine showed that in most cases, phytodesign has not become widespread.

Fig. 8. Fitness halls, Ukraine (Kyiv, Odesa)

Current trends in phytodesign include *vertical gardening; use of phytomodules and panels; living mono- and polystenes; zoning of space with designer compositions, portable and stationary phytopanel; decorating individual rooms with phytopaintings; scaling, zoning and organization of recreational areas* [9].

Currently, there are many currents and trends in interior landscaping with living and stabilized plants. As a method of eco-architecture, vertical landscaping, phytopaintings and fresh flowers standing in vases and pots are widely used in the interiors of fitness clubs. Such phytodesign always beautifies the room, provides coziness, creates a pleasant atmosphere and increases the artistic quality of decorative decoration. Vertical landscaping directly forms the interior of the room, enriches the architectural expressiveness of its interior space, improves its functional organization, performs aesthetic and utilitarian functions. A "living" wall is a structure with various plants that are mounted on the wall, and when using it, the issues of physical and aesthetic connection of plants and their care are solved. In addition to the aesthetic "living" wall, it can perform a protective function thanks to the improvement of the microclimate, ionization, cleaning, humidification, and enrichment of the air with oxygen. It provides regulation of the thermal regime, prevention of excessive heating of the walls, protection against noise, rain, wind, and dust (Fig. 9).

Fig. 9. Stabilized moss

According to the rules of phytodesign, the distribution of individual colors or groups of plants in interiors can be very diverse. At the same time, plant compositions should not conflict with the environment. It is very important to consider the size and purpose of the room when choosing and placing colors for landscaping. Therefore, large specimens are placed in the space of the room, small ones - in small rooms. In large halls, not overloaded with furniture, halls, it is better to put large tall plants with large leaves.

The humid air of gyms, locker rooms and swimming pools is a breeding ground for the growth of mold, bacteria, fungi and viruses, which is why a musty smell appears. Developing in the pool, showers and changing rooms, fungal colonies harm health and destroy sports equipment. The technical solution to the above problems is a properly designed ventilation system and the use of green plants.

Landscaping of indoor swimming pools of fitness centers has become a find for interior design (Fig. 10).

Fig. 10. Phytodisan of indoor pools

In the pool, you can use modern decor from plants. This is an opportunity to create a unique microclimate, a sense of comfort. When creating such a phytodesign, not only the harmony of the composition is taken into account, but also the ability of plants to survive in conditions of increased temperature, humidity and artificial lighting. Particular attention is paid to the selection of pots, which will also be exposed to the influence of a humid climate. A closed pool has its own characteristics, therefore unpretentious plants are used for landscaping the territory:

decorative palm trees; ficuses; decorative ivy; spathiphyllums; ferns, etc. Pots, planters and containers for plants are selected so that they are combined with plants and the general design of the indoor pool [10].

OBJECT, SUBJECT AND RESEARCH METHODS

Research object: fitness center project located in Odessa (Ukraine).

The purpose of the study: to develop internal landscaping of the premises of the fitness center as a way to improve air quality and microclimate.

The subject of the study: Identifying the peculiarities of the organization of fitness centers, taking into account sanitary and hygienic requirements for sports facilities.

Objectives of the study:

1. Conduct an analysis of the history of the formation and development of sports facilities;
2. Analyze the architectural and planning structure and experience in designing sports facilities;
3. Identify the factors affecting the air quality of gyms and fitness centers, and consider the sanitary and hygienic requirements for the microclimate;
4. To analyze the current state of phytodesign of interiors of fitness centers in foreign and domestic practice;
6. Identify relevant design solutions that can be used for landscaping the fitness center in the Odesa project.

Research methods. Use of a system approach in solving tasks. General scientific methods are applied in the research - study of literary sources, theoretical analysis, comparison, systematization, generalization of theoretical observations on modern directions of green architecture.

RESULTS

The construction of the fitness center is planned on the site located near the recreation area of Odesa, Ukraine (Fig. 11). The building is the compositional center of the entire territory. The project of the fitness center building was developed in accordance with the DBN of Ukraine. The topography of the territory is calm, the climate is moderate. The average annual temperature is $+10.7^{\circ}\text{C}$, the average annual precipitation is 425 mm. North and south-west winds prevail in winter, north-west and north in summer. Thus, climatic factors are favorable for designing a fitness center in this area. Climatic factors are favorable for the facility in this area

The spatial and planning solutions of the building include a gym, premises for group and individual classes, a swimming pool, sports fields and a tennis court. From the characteristics of the architectural and spatial organization of interiors, the dimensions of the room - its useful area, depth, height, area set aside for plants - serve as criteria for their landscaping; from the characteristics of the microclimate - the parameters of comfortable conditions for humans.

Fig. 11. The building of the fitness center

The project used modern methods of landscaping the interior spaces. As you know, the plants in the room decorate not only improve the appearance, but also improve the air quality. Plants emit more than 300 volatile substances that have a healing effect on the human body. Taking into account the sanitary and hygienic requirements, ornamental leafy plants, as well as undemanding and non-smelling crops were used in the project for the fitness center.

When creating the decorative decoration of the premises with the help of plants, the project used modern methods of vertical landscaping - phytowalls and panel paintings (phytopaintings). These new popular trends in phytodesign are most often used to save space. Phytopaintings are aesthetic and spectacular and have a positive visual and psychoemotional impact on visitors. This use of landscaping creates a concentration of living green mass, which contributes to the release of more oxygen. Plants provide freshness, humidification and cooling of the air, which is extremely important for the gym. All together helps the air conditioning system clean the air more efficiently. At the same time, the vertical landscaping of these premises provides additional noise insulation. Greening of columns and walls allows you to create accents in the interior, give the space more light and warmth.

In the premises of the fitness center (halls, corridors, lobby), a combination of vertical green compositions with single flowers is designed (Fig. 12). For the foyer, they chose to create a phytocomposition with a central part and more low-growing plants on the edges. Large and tall plants are placed on the floor or on a stand. At the same time, it was taken into account that flowers should not stand where they are easily damaged, for example, in narrow passages, in drafts, close to batteries, heaters and air conditioners.

The pool hall was not overloaded with a large number of green plants, vertical greening of the walls was used (Fig. 13). Individual plants in tubs or on the floor were not used because they can clutter the interior, block lighting and create inconvenience in movement, which do not correspond to the intended purpose of the

room. The coach's room also featured vertical landscaping and fresh flowers in vases placed on shelves.

Fig. 12. Phytodesign of the foyer

Fig. 13. Eco-design of the swimming pool and training room

The lack of space in training halls limits the use of many techniques of phytodesign. Landscaping in training halls should not interfere with training in the first place (Fig. 14). From a practical point of view, it is impractical to fill the space with a large number of single living plants. They interfere with the performance of exercises, require considerable means and care. Therefore, phytowalls and panel paintings (phytopaintings) were used in the training halls.

Fig. 14. Phytodesign of training halls

In the premises of the cafe, vertical greening of the walls was mainly used to create a micro-landscape suitable for this premises (Fig. 15). Individual plants in tubs or on the floor can clutter the interior of the cafe, block the lighting, create inconvenience in movement that do not correspond to the intended purpose of the room.

Fig. 15. Phytodesign cafe

Rest areas are provided for full relaxation and rest (Fig. 16). Taking into account the ratio of the size of the flower composition and the size of the room, it is proposed to arrange a small winter garden on the roof.

Fig. 16. Zone for repair

For the zone, curly growths were planted in the adjoining vicor. In order to visually visualize the zone of repair, creating a whole composition, greenery is placed behind the armchairs, symmetrically along the sides.

CONCLUSIONS

1. Among sports facilities in Ukraine, fitness clubs have the largest market share in cities. This is due to popularization of fitness at the highest level and stimulation of Ukrainians to a healthy lifestyle.

2. A high level of dust, carbon dioxide, formaldehyde and other volatile organic compounds is established in sports halls. Concentrations of these substances mostly exceed indoor air quality standards.

3. One of the main requirements for the design of modern fitness centers is the principle of environmental safety, which takes into account microclimatic and sanitary and hygienic requirements for the parameters of the premises.

4. The analysis of the international experience of designing fitness facilities showed that great attention is paid in the projects to the application of ecological and innovative solutions that meet the requirements of green construction.

5. An actual and promising direction in the architecture of sports facilities is the use of interior landscaping. Phytodesign of the internal space of sports centers solves a number of tasks: aesthetic - mental impact of plants on a person;

improvement of the air environment; disinfection and improvement of the environment due to volatile phytoncides; air purification from gases, dust, smoke; noise reduction.

6. The fitness center project (Odesa) used modern methods of interior landscaping - vertical landscaping, phyto-paintings and fresh flowers in vases.

7. The introduction of phytodesign will increase the environmental friendliness of the building, the comfort level of the stay, and the aesthetic architecture of the building.

8. The proposed architectural-planning solution will improve the microclimate and sanitary-hygienic characteristics of the indoor environment, as well as ensure the environmental compliance of the project with the requirements of green certification.

References:

1. Шипилов Р.В. История возникновения и развития спортивных сооружений [Electronic resource] <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/istoriya-vozniknoveniya-i-razvitiya-sportivnyh-sooruzheniy>

2. Краткая история развития спортивных сооружений [Electronic resource] <https://poznayka.org/s124688t2.html>

3. Жданова И.В., Кузнецова А.А., Михайлина П.И. Архитектурно-планировочные принципы организации фитнес-центров. Вестник БГТУ им. В.Г. Шухова. 2019. №10, С.84-92.

[Electronic resource] <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/arhitekturno-planirovochnye-printsipy-organizatsii-fines-tsentrov/viewer>

4. Требования к тренажерному залу. СанПиН для фитнес-клуба. [Electronic resource] <https://fitclub.ru/blog/detail/trebovaniya-k-trenazhernomu-zalu-sanpin-v-fitness-klube/>

5. ДБН В.2.2-13-2003. Будинки і споруди. Спортивні і фізкультурно-оздоровчі споруди. Київ 2004 136с. [Electronic resource]

http://www.specteh.org.ua/images/stories/normativnye_dokumenty/dbn_v.2.2-13-2003

6. Декоративне мистецтво в художньому оформленні інтер'єрів. [Electronic resource] https://studopedia.com.ua/1_56166_ozelenennya-primishchen-gotel'nogo-gospodarstva.html

7. Electronic resource <https://elibrary.petrsu.ru/book.shtml?id=22768>

8. Гаврилова О.И. Озеленение интерьеров [Electronic resource] https://www.studmed.ru/gracheva-av-osnovy-fitodizayna_15bf9e5ae70.html

9. Тисленко А.А., Шаповалова Н.М., Самойленко П.В. Современные приемы внедрения озеленения в интерьер жилого пространства. [Electronic resource] <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/sovremennye-priemy-vnedreniya-ozeleneniya-v-interier-zhilogo-prostranstva>

10. [Electronic resource] <https://designerdreamhomes.ru/50-exciting-ideas-for-indoor-swimming-pools/>